

Non-Isomorphism Between Graph And Its Complement

Wafiq Hibi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Isomorphism between Two Graphs, Complementary Graph, Complete Graph</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4965942</p>	<p><i>It is known that any graph with six vertices cannot be isomorphic to its complement [3]. V. K. Balakrishnan has written in his book Schaum's solved problems series [1] the following: "Given two arbitrary Simple graphs of the same order and the same size, the problem of determining whether an isomorphism exists between the two is known as the isomorphism problem in graph theory. In general, it is not all easy (in other words, there is no "efficient algorithm") to solve an arbitrary instance of the isomorphism problem", from here came the idea of this paper. As mentioned, isomorphism between two graphs G_1 and G_2 is a one-valued function that copies the vertices of graph G_1 over all the vertices of graph G_2. If two vertices connected on edge in graph G_1, their images will be connected on edge in graph G_2; also, if two vertices are not connected on edge on graph G_1 so their images will also not be connected on edge also on graph G_2. The complementary graph of graph G and which will be marked with G^-, is defined as the graph that contains the same set of vertices, and two vertices connected on edge in graph G will be connected on edge in graph G^-, and two non-connected vertices on edge in graph G will be non-connected vertices on edge in graph G^-. The purpose of this paper is to present an enough condition on the vertex number of a given graph so that it is not isomorphic to its complement.</i></p>

Introduction

Let K_n denote the complete graph having n vertices; since this graph contains all possible edges then, $\binom{n}{2} = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ will give its number of edges, [3].

In graph theory a graph G should consist of an orderly pair of two sets (V, E) , when V marks the vertex set of the graph, and when E marks the set of edges of this graph, and is usually marked with $|V| = n, |E| = m$ to the Number of vertices and edges of the graph respectively.

The complementary graph of $G: (V, E)$ is the graph $\bar{G}: (V, \bar{E})$, and it is the graph built on the same vertices, with the inversion of the edges, where there was an edge in the original graph there is no edge in the complementary graph, and where there was no edges, there is an edge in the complementary graph.

Graphs $G: (V_1, E_2)$ and $H: (V_2, E_2)$ are isomorphic if there is a function $\rho: V_1 \rightarrow V_2$ one-valued and on, so that for all $x, y \in V_1$ the number of edges connecting between x and y is the same as the number of edges connecting between $\rho(x)$ and $\rho(y)$.

Two graphs $G: (V_1, E_2)$ and $H: (V_2, E_2)$, which are isomorphic to each other, will be marked as follows $G \cong H$, and a simple conclusion from this isomorphism is that $|V_1| = |V_2|$ and $|E_1| = |E_2|$.

The purpose of this paper is to provide a formula for the vertices of any graphs G , so that if this number of vertices maintains it, it will not be isomorphic to its complementary graph \bar{G} .

New result:

The new result presented in the following theorem:

Theorem:

Let $\{n_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ be a series of natural numbers, which given by:

$$\begin{cases} n_1 = 2 \\ n_i = b + n_{i-1} \end{cases} \quad (i \geq 2)$$

When $b = 1$ or $b = 3$, when i is an even number $n_i = 3 + n_{i-1}$ and when i is an odd number $n_i = 1 + n_{i-1}$.

No member in the series $\{n_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ can be used as a vertex number of a graph G when $G \cong \bar{G}$.

Proof:

Let $G = (V, E)$, when $|V| = n, |E| = m_1$ and let $\bar{G} = (\bar{V}, \bar{E})$ denote the complementary graph of G , when $|\bar{V}| = n, |\bar{E}| = m_2$, so it is clear that:

$$G \cup \bar{G} = (V, E \cup \bar{E}) = K_{|V|}, \text{ and } |E \cup \bar{E}| = m_1 + m_2 = \binom{|V|}{2} = \binom{n}{2} = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}.$$

To keep it clear, we divide the proof of the theorem into three steps:

Step1:

If $G \cong \bar{G}$ then $m_1 = |E| = |\bar{E}| = m_2 := m$, so $2m = \binom{n}{2}$ too, it follows as a necessary condition that the number $\binom{n}{2}$ there must be an even number. Moreover, if $\binom{n}{2}$ is an odd number, that would be enough to make G and \bar{G} not isomorphic.

So let $\binom{n}{2} = 2k-1$, k is a natural number $k \geq 1$, the last equation, is the quadratic equation,

$$n^2 - n - 4k + 2 = 0 \text{ whose solution is given by } n_{1,2} = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{16k-7}}{2}, \text{ then we will actually get that } n = \frac{1 + \sqrt{16k-7}}{2},$$

(Since n must be a natural number).

Step2:

We will now look for which natural values for n , will be obtained from $n = \frac{1 + \sqrt{16k-7}}{2}$, because these are exactly the values that we are looking for, and for them the value $\binom{n}{2}$ is an odd number.

The following table shows the first values of n (From now on, we will mark them with $n_i, i \geq 1$) in relation to k :

k	i	n_i
1	1	2
2	2	3
8	3	6
10	4	7
23	5	10
28	6	11
46	7	14
53	8	15
77	9	18
86	10	19
.	.	.
.	.	.
.	.	.

It follows that the series corresponding to the values of n_i is:

2, 3, 6, 7, 10, 11, 14, 15, 18, 19, 21, 22, ...

In fact, we can split this series into the following two series:

The series of members that are in an odd index: 2, 6, 10, 14, 18, 22, ...

Which is an Arithmetic progression, so we can write it according: $n_i = 4i - 3$.

The series of members that are in an even index: 3, 7, 11, 15, 19, 23, ...

Which is an Arithmetic progression, so we can write it according: $n_i = 4i - 1$.

It is clear that this Arithmetic progression can be combined in the next recursive series:

$$\begin{cases} n_1 = 2 \\ n_i = b + n_{i-1} \quad (i \geq 2) \end{cases}$$

When $b = 1$ or $b = 3$, when i is an even number $n_i = 3 + n_{i-1}$ and when i is an odd number $n_i = 1 + n_{i-1}$.

Step3:

Let us now prove that no member in the series $\{n_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ can be used as a vertex number of a graph G when $G \cong \bar{G}$.

To do this, it is sufficient to prove that the natural number $\binom{n_i}{2}$ is an odd number, for all $i \geq 1$.

The proof will be based on induction for the index i .

It will obviously happen when $i \geq 1$:

Then $n_1 = 2$ and $\binom{2}{2} = 1$, it is an odd number.

Suppose now that $\binom{n_i}{2}$ is an odd number for $i = s$, this means that:

$$\frac{n_s(n_s-1)}{2}, \text{ is an odd number.}$$

Now we will prove that $\binom{n_{s+1}}{2}$ is an odd number, this means we will prove that:

$$\frac{n_{s+1}(n_{s+1}-1)}{2}, \text{ is an odd number.}$$

To do this, we differentiate between two cases:

First case:

The index s is an odd number, so n_s will be an even number, and $n_{s+1} = 1 + n_s$

Add to that:

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{n_{s+1}}{2} &= \\ &= \frac{n_{s+1}(n_{s+1}-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(n_s+1)(n_s+1-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(n_s+1)n_s}{2} \\ &= \frac{n_s(n_s-1)}{2} + n_s, \end{aligned}$$

The number $\frac{n_s(n_s-1)}{2}$ is an odd number from the imposition of induction, and the number n_s is an even number, it follows that $\binom{n_{s+1}}{2}$ is an odd number.

The second case:

The index s is an even number, then n_s will be an odd number, and $n_{s+1} = 3 + n_s$,

Add to that

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{n_{s+1}}{2} &= \\ &= \frac{n_{s+1}(n_{s+1}-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(n_s+3)(n_s+3-1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(n_s+3)(n_s+2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{n_s^2 + 5n_s + 6}{2} \\ &= \frac{n_s(n_s-1) + 6n_s + 6}{2} \\ &= \frac{n_s(n_s-1)}{2} + 3(n_s+1) \end{aligned}$$

The number $\frac{n_s(n_s-1)}{2}$ is an odd number from the imposition of induction, and the number $3(n_s+1)$ is an even number, it follows that $\binom{n_{s+1}}{2}$ is an odd number.

This completes the proof of the theorem.

References

- Balakrishnan, V. K. (1997). Theory and problems of graph theory. Schaum's solved problems series McGraw-Hill.
- Cheng, Ji. (2011). the necessary condition of isomorphism for self-complementary graph. International Conference on Multimedia Technology, 10.1109/ICMT.2011.6002684, pp. 2716-2718.
- Goodaire, E., Parmenter, G. (2002). Discrete mathematics with graph theory -2nd Edition. Prentice Hall, Inc
- Vilfred, V. (2017). A few properties of circulant graphs: Self-complementary, isomorphism, Cartesian product and factorization, Simulation, and Applied Optimization (ICMSAO), pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICMSAO.2017.7934923.

Author Information

Wafiq Hibi

Assistant Professor

Head of the Mathematics Department in Sakhnin

College. The Academic College of Sakhnin
